

Syntheses of Furano Compounds. Part XL. Cyclisation of 3-Phenylbenzo [b] furan-2-acetic acid. A Revision of Earlier Structures

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The products obtained by the cyclisation of 3-arybenzo [b] furan-2-acetic acids with phosphoric anhydride in benzene are shown to be the esters (IX). The phenol (VIIa) has been synthesised.

JOHNSON and Robertson¹ subjected 6-methoxy-3-*p*-methoxyphenylbenzo[b] furan-2-acetic acid (III) to cyclisation with phosphorus pentoxide in benzene and suggested a structure (VIIb) for the cyclised product. Chatterjea and Srivastava² also investigated the cyclisation reaction with 3-phenylbenzo[b]furan-2-acetic acid (I) and erroneously

proposed the cyclobutenone structure (VIII). As a result of detailed chemical and spectral investigations it has now been established that these are neither phenols nor cyclobutenones but esters of the type (IX).

- I, R = R₂ = H, R₁ = CH₂COOH
 II, R = H, R₂ = CH₃, R₁ = CH₂COOH
 III, R = R₂ = OCH₃, R₁ = CH₂COOH
 IV, R = R₂ = H, R₁ = CH₂CONH₂
 V, R = R₂ = H, R₁ = CH₂C(CH₃)₂OH
 VI, R = R₂ = H, R₁ = CH₂.CH₂OH

- IXa, R = R₁ = H
 IXb, R = H, R₁ = CH₃
 IXc, R = R₁ = OCH₃

- VIIa, R = R₁ = H
 VIIb, R = R₁ = OCH₃

VIII

Thus 3-phenylbenzo[b] furan-2-acetic acid (I), 3-*p*-tolylbenzo[b]furan-2-acetic acid (II) and 6-methoxy-3-*p*-methoxyphenylbenzo[b]furan-2-acetic acid (III) were prepared (*vide* experimental) from the corresponding 3-arylbenzofuran and were cyclised to the esters (IXa), (IXb) and (IXc) respectively. These esters showed i.r. absorptions at 1753, 1750 and 1746 cm⁻¹ respectively for the ester carbonyl groups. The NMR spectrum of (IXa) showed eighteen aromatic protons around τ 2.4 and two protons at τ 5.66 as a singlet for -CH₂COO- while that of (IXb) showed sixteen aromatic protons around τ 2.6, a singlet of two protons at τ 5.75 for -CH₂COO- and two other singlets each of three protons at τ 7.65 and τ 7.8 for the aromatic methyl groups. The high resolution mass spectra of (IXa) and (IXb) showed molecular ion peaks at *m/e* 468 and 496 respectively.

The authentic phenol 5-Hydroxybenzo[b]naphtho [1,2-d] furan (VIIa) was independently synthesised from 3-methoxy-2-acetyldibenzofuran or 3-methoxydibenzofuran^{3,4} (*vide* Chart I). This authentic phenol

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(VIIa) was found to be different from the cyclised product (IXa). It gave an acetate and coupled with diazonium salts to give azo dyes. The i.r. spectrum did not show any carbonyl absorption but showed a phenolic hydroxyl absorption at 3320 cm^{-1} . Oxidation of the phenol (VIIa) with Fremy's salt gave the related *o*-quinone (X).

The ester structure has also been proved on the basis of following chemical reactions. Hydrolysis of the ester (IXa) with aqueous alcoholic sodium carbonate solution afforded the acid (I) and the dinaphthol (XI) (M^+ , 466). The dinaphthol (XI) could also be obtained from the phenol (VIIa) by oxidative coupling in alkaline solution in presence of air or with a base such as CH_3MgI . Reaction

Chart I

of the ester (IXa) with alcoholic ammonia gave mainly the amide (IV). Reaction with methylamine and aniline gave the corresponding amide and anilide respectively. With methylmagnesium iodide (IXa) gave a mixture of (V), (VIIa) and (XI). Reduction of (IXa) with lithium aluminium hydride gave mixture of alcohol (VI), phenol (VIIa) and the dinaphthol (XI).

Experimental

Melting and boiling points are uncorrected. IR spectra were recorded in a Perkin Elmer Infrared spectrophotometer, Model 237 in KBr discs and the NMR spectra were obtained in a 60 MHz instrument in deuterio-chloroform using tetramethylsilane as an internal standard.

3-Acetoxydibenzofuran : 3-Hydroxydibenzofuran (6 g) was acetylated by refluxing it with acetic anhydride (20 ml) in presence of catalytic amount of concentrated sulphuric acid for 15 min to afford 3-acetoxydibenzofuran (5 g), m.p. $109^\circ\text{--}11^\circ$. (Found : C, 74.0; H, 4.7, $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 74.3; H, 4.5%).

3-Methoxy-2-acetyldibenzofuran : Finely powdered anhydrous aluminium chloride (4 g) was added in portions with shaking to a solution of 3-acetoxydibenzofuran (6 g) in *sym*-tetrachloroethane (40 ml) preheated to 60° . The mixture was refluxed for 1 hr with shaking. On working up in the usual manner 3-hydroxy-2-acetyldibenzofuran (3.5 g) was obtained which crystallised from ethyl alcohol in yellow needles, m.p. $150^\circ\text{--}52^\circ$, (Found : C, 74.3; H, 5.0, $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 74.3; H, 4.5%) ν_{max} 1650 cm^{-1} (chelated carbonyl), $3440\text{--}3460\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (chelated hydroxyl).

The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from nitrobenzene as red needles, m.p. $>300^\circ$ (Found : N, 13.6, $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_6\text{N}_4$ requires N, 13.8%).

The above phenol was methylated in the usual way with dimethyl sulphate to give 3-methoxy-2-acetyldibenzofuran crystallising from ethyl alcohol in colourless prisms, m.p. $110^\circ\text{--}12^\circ$ (Found : C, 75.4; H, 5.4, $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 75.0; H, 5.0%) ν_{max} 1670 cm^{-1} (carbonyl).

The same compound was also prepared by direct acetylation (AlCl_3) of 3-methoxydibenzofuran under cold condition.

The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from acetic acid in orange needles, m.p. $248^\circ\text{--}49^\circ$ (Found : N, 13.3, $\text{C}_{21}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_6\text{N}_4$ requires N, 13.3%).

3-Methoxy-2- ω -bromoacetyldibenzofuran : The above ketone (0.4 g) in chloroform (5 ml) was brominated with bromine (0.3 g) in chloroform (5 ml) at 10° . After keeping the mixture at room temperature for half an hour, it was worked up as usual to afford the bromo-ketone (0.35 g), m.p. $169^\circ\text{--}70^\circ$ (benzene). (Found : C, 56.5; H, 3.0, $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_3\text{Br}$ requires C, 56.4; H, 3.4%).

β -(3-Methoxy-2-dibenzofuryl)propionic Acid : 3-Methoxy-2- ω -bromoacetyldibenzofuran (1 g) was condensed with sodiomalonic ester (from 0.1 g Na and 0.69 g diethylmalonate) under reflux in benzene for 3 hr to give the corresponding diester which on hydrolysis with methanolic sodium hydroxide and subsequent acidification gave the dicarboxylic acid. This was decarboxylated by heating in an oil bath at $185^\circ\text{--}95^\circ$ for 10 min to give the desired β -(3-methoxy-2-dibenzofuryl)propionic acid (0.1 g). This was crystallised from acetic acid as light brown needles, m.p. $195^\circ\text{--}96^\circ$ (Found : C, 68.3; H, 4.2, $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_5$ requires C, 68.5; H, 4.7%) ν_{max} 1660 cm^{-1} (keto carbonyl) and 1705 cm^{-1} (acid carbonyl).

The same acid was also prepared by succinoylation with succinic anhydride and anhydrous aluminium chloride in nitrobenzene at $0^\circ\text{--}5^\circ$.

γ -(3-Methoxy-2-dibenzofuryl)butyric Acid : The above acid (0.55 g) in diethylene glycol (2.5 ml) containing potassium hydroxide (0.4 g) was treated

with hydrazine hydrate (0.5 ml, 99%) and heated mildly on water bath for 1½ hr. After removal of water under reduced pressure the mixture was heated at 185°–90° for 3 hr. On working up in the usual manner a thick oil was obtained which was chromatographed over silica gel using benzene as eluent to afford solid (0.25 g) crystallising from benzene in colourless needles, m.p. 112°–13° (Found: C, 71.2; H, 6.1, C₁₇H₁₆O₄ requires C, 71.8; H, 5.7%).

The same acid was also obtained by reducing the above keto-acid by Clemmensen method.

Cyclisation of γ -(3-Methoxy-2-dibenzofuryl) butyric Acid: The above acid (0.5 g) was cyclised by heating it with polyphosphoric acid [P₂O₅ (3 g) and phosphoric acid (2.5 ml)] at 165°–70° for 5 hr. The reaction mixture was worked up as usual to give a crude product (0.35 g) which was purified by chromatography over alumina column. The tetralone was crystallised from methyl alcohol as light yellow needles, m.p. 102°–04° (Found: C, 77.2; H, 5.3, C₁₇H₁₄O₂ requires C, 76.7; H, 5.3%) ν_{max} 1672 cm⁻¹ (carbonyl).

The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone was crystallised from acetic acid as orange red needles, m.p. 269°–71° (Found: C, 61.4; H, 4.4, C₂₃H₁₈O₆N₄ requires C, 61.9; H, 4.1%).

5-Methoxybenzo[b]naphtho[1,2-d]furan: The foregoing tetralone (0.25 g) in dry ether (20 ml) was stirred with a slurry of lithium aluminium hydride (0.25 g) in dry ether (5 ml) at room temperature for 2 hr. The mixture was worked up as usual to give a cotton like material crystallising from benzene in colourless needles, m.p. 168°. This was dehydrogenerated by heating with palladised charcoal (0.05 g; 10%) at 270°–280° for 1 hr to afford the desired 5-methoxybenzo[b]naphtho[1,2-d]furan, m.p. 97°–98° (petroleum ether). (Found: C, 81.9; H, 5.2, C₁₇H₁₂O₂ requires C, 82.2; H, 4.9%).

5-Hydroxybenzo[b]naphtho[1,2-d]furan: The aforesaid methyl ester (0.7 g) in glacial acetic acid (10 ml) was demethylated by refluxing with hydrobromic acid (3.5 ml; 48%) for 8 hr. The resulting phenol (0.5 g) was crystallised from benzene in colourless shining needles, m.p. 158°–60° (Found: C, 81.5; H, 4.8, C₁₆H₁₀O₂ requires C, 82.0; H, 4.3%) ν_{OH} 3320 cm⁻¹. The acetate had m.p. 137°–39° (Found: C, 78.7; H, 5.2, C₁₈H₁₂O₃ requires C, 78.3; H, 4.4%) ν_{max} 1760 cm⁻¹ (ester carbonyl).

Oxidation of 5-Hydroxybenzo[b]naphtho[1,2-d]furan: The above phenol (50 mg) in acetone (10 ml) was oxidised with a mixture of potassium nitrosodisulphonate (0.5 g) in water (15 ml) and potassium hydrogen phosphate (3.4 ml; M/6). Removal of acetone after filtration yielded the quinone which was converted into quinoxaline derivative by heating the compound in acetic acid with *o*-phenylenediamine. The compound separated as shining yellow needles, m.p. 242°–44° from acetic acid. (Found: C, 82.3; H, 4.0, C₂₂H₁₂ON₂ requires C, 82.5; H, 3.8%).

The phenol was also oxidised by Jones' reagent⁶ in pure acetone. The reaction mixture was worked up as usual to give red residue from which the

quinoxaline derivative was prepared in a similar manner.

3-Phenylbenzofuran: *o*-Phenoxyacetophenone (14 g) was added to polyphosphoric acid from phosphorus pentoxide (105 g) and syrupy phosphoric acid (50 ml) preheated to 80°–82° and the mixture was heated at this temperature for 4 hr with continuous stirring. On working up, 3-phenylbenzofuran (11 g) b.p. 140°–42°/1 mm was obtained (lit.⁶ b.p. 110°/0.3 mm).

2-Formyl-3-Phenylbenzofuran: A mixture of 3-phenylbenzofuran (4 g) dimethylformamide (2 ml) and phosphorus oxychloride (3.6 ml) was heated on water bath for 3 hr. On working up, 2-formyl-3-phenylbenzofuran (4.3 g) was obtained which crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether in colourless stout needles, m.p. 65°–67° (Found: C, 80.9; H, 4.9, C₁₅H₁₀O₂ requires C, 81.1; H, 4.5%).

3-Phenylbenzo[b]furan-2-carboxylic Acid: The above aldehyde (5 g) was refluxed with silver nitrate solution (110 ml; 8%). Sodium hydroxide solution (25 ml; 15%) was added dropwise in 25 min. The refluxing was continued for 1 hr more till the silver mirror crust was disintegrated. It was worked up in usual manner to afford 3-phenylbenzo[b]furan-2-carboxylic acid (4.5 g), m.p. 232°–34° (acetic acid) (lit.⁷, m.p. 234°, different preparation).

3-Phenylbenzo[b]furan-2-acetic Acid: This was prepared from 3-phenylbenzo[b]furan-2-carboxylic acid by Arndt-Eistert reaction following the known procedure⁷.

Cyclisation of 3-phenylbenzo[b]furan-2-acetic Acid: The above acid (0.2 g) was added to polyphosphoric acid from phosphorus pentoxide (5 g) and phosphoric acid (2 ml) and the mixture was heated with stirring for 2 hr at 100°. On working up in the usual manner, the ester (IXa) was obtained which crystallised from benzene as colourless needles, m.p. 151°–52° identical with the product obtained by cyclisation with phosphorus pentoxide in benzene (lit.⁷ m.p. 142°) M⁺, m/e = 468 ν_{max} 1753 cm⁻¹ (ester carbonyl).

Reaction of the Ester (IXa) with Alcoholic sodium carbonate solution:

The ester (IXa) (0.1 g) was refluxed with a mixture of sodium carbonate solution (3 ml; 10%) and ethyl alcohol (6 ml) for 6 hr. The solvent was removed under reduced pressure, the residue was diluted with water, filtered, dried and crystallised from benzene in colourless shining needles, m.p. >360° presumed to be dinaphthol (XI) (Found: C, 81.9; H, 4.2, C₃₂H₁₈O₄ requires C, 82.4; H, 3.9%) M⁺, m/e = 466 ν_{max} 3520 cm⁻¹ (hydroxyl).

Its acetate was prepared and crystallised from acetic acid as light cream coloured tiny plates, m.p. 305°–07° (Found: C, 78.7; H, 4.2, C₃₆H₂₂O₆ requires C, 78.5; H, 4.0%) ν_{max} 1772 cm⁻¹ (ester carbonyl).

The filtrate (obtained from the hydrolysis reaction described above) was acidified with dilute hydrochloric acid to give 3-phenylbenzo[b]furan-2-acetic acid, m.p. and mixed m.p. 144°.

Oxidative dimerisation of 5-Hydroxybenzo[b]naphtho[1,2-d]furan: The authentic phenol (VIIa) (50 ml) in dry benzene (8 ml) was added with shaking to a cold ethereal solution of methylmagnesium iodide from Mg (0.2 g), CH_3I (0.8 g) and the reaction mixture was left overnight. After working up in the usual manner, the dinaphthol (XI) (40 mg) was obtained which was crystallised from benzene as silky needles, m.p. $> 360^\circ$. The identity was confirmed by comparison of i.r. spectra.

Reaction of the Ester (IXa) with Aqueous Alcoholic Ammonia: The ester (IXa) (0.1 g) was treated with alcohol (20 ml) and liquor ammonia (0.5 ml) and refluxed on water bath for 8 hr. On working up 3-phenylbenzo[b]furan-2-acetamide was obtained, m.p. and mixed m.p. $180^\circ\text{--}82^\circ$, 3-Phenylbenzo[b]-Furan 2-N-methylacetamide, similarly prepared with methyl amine, crystallised from benzene in colourless needles, m.p. $176^\circ\text{--}77^\circ$ (Found: C, 76.7; H, 6.0, $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{15}\text{O}_2\text{N}$ requires C, 77.0; H, 5.7%) ν_{max} 1648 cm^{-1} and 3300 cm^{-1} . The corresponding acetanilide prepared by reaction with aniline, crystallised from acetic acid as colourless needles, m.p. $192^\circ\text{--}93^\circ$ (Found: C, 80.6; H, 5.4, $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{17}\text{O}_2\text{N}$ requires C, 80.7; H, 5.2%) ν_{max} 1662 cm^{-1} (anilide carbonyl), 3298 cm^{-1} (NH).

Action of Lithium Aluminium Hydride on the Ester (IXa): The suspension of the ester (0.1 g) in dry ether (25 ml) was stirred with a slurry of lithium aluminium hydride (0.1 g) in dry ether (5 ml) at room temperature for $1\frac{1}{2}$ hr. On working up, a solid was obtained which crystallised from benzene to give 5-hydroxybenzo[b]naphtho[1,2-d]furan, m.p. and mixed m.p. $159^\circ\text{--}61^\circ$.

The mother liquor was concentrated and chromatographed over alumina column to afford 3-phenylbenzo[b]furan-2-ethanol crystallising from benzene-petroleum ether as shining needles, m.p. $79^\circ\text{--}81^\circ$, identical with an authentic specimen prepared by reduction of methyl 3-phenylbenzo[b]furan-2-acetate with lithium aluminium hydride as usual. (Found: C, 81.3; H, 6.1, $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_2$ required C, 80.6; H, 5.9%) ν_{max} 3240 cm^{-1} (hydroxyl). NMR spectrum showed resonance at around $\tau 2.53$ (9H, aromatic), $\tau 5.98$ (triplet, 2H, CH_2), $\tau 6.88$ (triplet, 2H, CH_2) and $\tau 8.37$ (singlet, 1H, OH).

When the reaction product was decomposed after leaving it overnight, an additional product was obtained along with the products mentioned above crystallising from acetic acid as colourless silky needles, m.p. $> 360^\circ$ and identified as (XI).

Reaction of the Ester (IXa) with methylmagnesium Iodide: A solution of the ester (IXa) (0.3 g) in dry benzene (10 ml) was added to methylmagnesium iodide from magnesium (0.2 g) and methyl iodide (0.8 g) with shaking and allowed to stand for half an hour. On working up in the usual manner a solid was obtained which crystallised from benzene as colourless needles, m.p. $160^\circ\text{--}62^\circ$ identical with the authentic phenol (VIIa).

The mother liquor was concentrated and chromatographed over alumina column to give a carbinol m.p. $105^\circ\text{--}07^\circ$ identical with the product obtained

from a similar reaction with methyl 3-phenylbenzo[b]furan-2-acetate, (Found: C, 81.5; H, 6.9, $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 81.2; H, 6.8%) ν_{max} 3353 cm^{-1} (tertiary hydroxyl). NMR spectrum showed resonance at around $\tau 2.55$ (9H, aromatic proton), $\tau 6.95$ (singlet,

The same reaction mixture when decomposed after leaving it overnight, afforded an additional product m.p. $> 360^\circ$ which was identical as (XI).

3-p-Tolylbenzofuran: *p*-Methyl- ω -phenoxyacetophenone (6 g) was added to a stirred polyphosphoric acid from phosphoric anhydride (50 g) and phosphoric acid (30 ml) maintained at 80° . The stirring was continued for 5 hr at the same temperature. On working up, a solid product was obtained which crystallised from alcohol to give colourless shining plates, m.p. $128^\circ\text{--}29^\circ$ of 2-*p*-tolylbenzofuran (1.7 g). The mother liquor was evaporated and distilled to give 3-*p*-tolylbenzofuran (3 g) as oil, b.p. $140^\circ\text{--}45^\circ/1\text{ mm}$ (Found: C, 86.1; H, 6.0, $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{10}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 86.5; H, 5.8%).

2-Formyl-3-p-tolylbenzofuran: A mixture of 3-*p*-tolylbenzofuran (6 g), *N,N*-dimethylformamide (3 ml) and phosphorus oxychloride (5 ml) was heated on water bath for 6 hr. It was worked up as usual to give 2-formyl-3-*p*-tolylbenzofuran (6.5 g) crystallising from petroleum ether as bright cream coloured slender needles, m.p. $91^\circ\text{--}92^\circ$ (Found: C, 81.2; H, 5.1, $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_2$ requires C, 81.3; H, 5.1%).

The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from acetic acid as orange needles, m.p. $220^\circ\text{--}22^\circ$ (Found: N, 13.8, $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_6\text{N}_4$ requires N, 13.5%).

3-p-Tolylbenzo[b]furan-2-carboxylic Acid: The above aldehyde was oxidised with silver nitrate and sodium hydroxide solution in a similar manner as described earlier to give 3-*p*-tolylbenzo[b]furan-2-carboxylic acid crystallising from acetic acid as yellow shining needles, m.p. $238^\circ\text{--}40^\circ$ (decomp.) (Found: C, 75.9; H, 5.1; $6\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{12}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 76.2; H, 4.8%).

3-p-Tolylbenzo[b]furan-2-acetic Acid: The foregoing acid (3 g) was converted into the acid chloride by the usual procedure and its suspension in dry ether was added slowly to dry ethereal diazomethane prepared from nitrosomethylurea (12 g) and left overnight in refrigerator. Removal of ether under reduced pressure afforded diazoketone, m.p. $109^\circ\text{--}11^\circ$. A solution of the diazoketone in pure dioxan (17 ml) was added gradually during half an hour to a solution of silver nitrate (40 ml; 10%) in liquor ammonia (30 ml) at 70° . After heating on water bath for 3 hr the reaction mixture was left overnight. On working

up, the amide (3 g) was obtained which crystallised from benzene as colourless needles, m.p. 170°–72° (Found : C, 76.9; H, 5.7, C₁₇H₁₅O₂N requires C, 77.0; H, 5.7%).

Hydrolysis of the amide with ethanolic potassium hydroxide in the usual manner afforded the 3-*p*-tolylbenzo[b]furan-2-acetic acid (2.5g) m.p. 163° (benzene). (Found : C, 76.3; H, 5.7, C₁₇H₁₄O₃ requires C, 76.7; H, 5.3%).

*Cyclisation of 3-*p*-tolylbenzo[b]furan-2-acetic Acid* : 3-*p*-Tolylbenzo[b]furan-2-acetic acid (1 g) was cyclised with polyphosphoric acid in a similar manner as in the cyclisation 3-phenylbenzo[b]furan-2-acetic acid to give the ester (LXb) (0.7 g). It was crystallised from benzene as light yellow needles, m.p. 165°–66°. (Found : C, 81.9; H, 5.1, C₂₄H₂₄O₄ requires C, 82.2; H, 4.9%) M⁺, m/c = 496, ν_{max} 1750 cm⁻¹ (ester carbonyl).

*2-Formyl-6-methoxy-3-*p*-methoxyphenylbenzofuran* : This compound was prepared from 6-methoxy-3-*p*-methoxyphenylbenzofuran by reaction with N,N-dimethyl formamide in presence of phosphorus oxychloride in similar way as described earlier. Crystallisation from ethyl alcohol provided colourless needles, m.p. 167° (lit.¹ m.p. 167°, different preparation).

*6-Methoxy-3-*p*-methoxyphenylbenzo[b]furan-2-carboxylic Acid* : The above aldehyde was oxidised in a similar manner described earlier to give the corresponding acid which was crystallised from acetic acid in cream coloured needles, m.p. 223° (decomp.) (lit.¹, m.p. 223°, different preparation).

*6-Methoxy-3-*p*-methoxyphenylbenzo [b]furan-2-acetic acid* : The foregoing acid (2.5 g) was converted into 6-methoxy-3-*p*-methoxyphenylbenzo [b]furan-2-acetamide (1 g) via the diazoketone, m.p. 150°–151° (decomp.) following the Arndt-Eistert procedure. The amide was crystallised from benzene in colourless needles, m.p. 210°–11° (lit.², m.p. 210°, different preparation). The amide on hydrolysis with methanolic potassium hydroxide and subsequent acidification yielded 6-methoxy-3-*p*-methoxyphenylbenzo[b]

furan-2-acetic acid which was crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether as colourless needles, m.p. 170° (lit.¹, m.p. 169°–70°, different preparation).

*Cyclisation of 6-Methoxy-3-*p*-methoxyphenylbenzo[b]furan-2-acetic Acid* : The above acid was also cyclised with phosphorus pentoxide in benzene in a similar way described earlier to give the ester (IXc). This was crystallised from acetic acid as colourless tiny needles, m.p. 182°–84° (lit.¹ m.p. 179°–80°; ν_{max} 1746 cm⁻¹ (ester carbonyl)).

Reaction of the Ester (IXc) with Lithium Aluminium Hydride : The above ester (0.1 g) was suspended in dry ether (20 ml) and stirred at room temperature with a slurry of lithium aluminium hydride (0.2 g) in dry ether (5 ml) for 1 hr. On working up a solid product was obtained which was triturated with warm sodium hydroxide solution (5%), filtered, washed with water, dried and crystallised from benzene-petroleum ether as colourless shining needles, m.p. 108°–10° of 6-methoxy-3-*p*-methoxyphenylbenzo[b]furan-2-ethanol. (Found : C, 72.6; H, 6.3, C₁₈H₁₈O₄ requires C, 72.5; H, 6.6%).

The alkaline filtrate gave solid later on m.p. > 360° identified as the corresponding dinaphthol which was converted into the diacetate crystallising from acetic acid as cream coloured tiny plates, m.p. 307°–309° (Found : C, 71.1; H, 4.8, C₄₀H₃₀O₁₀ requires C, 71.6; H, 4.5%) ν_{max} 1770 cm⁻¹.

References

1. P. C. JOHNSON and A. ROBERTSON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, 2381.
2. J. N. CHATTERJEA and S. SRIVASTAVA, *Experientia*, 1970, 26, 1291.
3. S. SHIBATA, S. S. NATORI and Y. SUMI, *J. Pharm. Soc. Japan*, 1952, 72, 1333.
4. S. YAMASIRO, *Bull. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 16, 6.
5. A. BOWERS, T. G. HALSALL, E. R. H. JONES and A. J. LEMIN, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, 2548.
6. W. DAVIS and S. MIDDLETON, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1958, 822.
7. J. N. CHATTERJEA, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1956, 33, 339.